

SYNTHESIS OF BENZONICOTINE

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A synthesis of benzonicotine has been described starting from ethyl quinoline-3-carboxylate and *N*-methylpyrrolid-2-one according to Späth's synthesis of nicotine from ethyl pyridine-3-carboxylate.

Späth's synthesis of nicotine from ethyl pyridine-3-carboxylate suggested the possibility of synthesising a compound from ethyl quinoline-3-carboxylate (Friedländer and Gohring, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 459; Stuart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, **53**, 143; Tafel and Wassmuth, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 2831) which could similarly be reacted with *N*-methylpyrrolid-2-one to give a benzonicotine (VII).

N-methylpyrrolid-2-one (II) (Tafel and Wassmuth, *loc. cit.*, Späth and Bertschneider, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 327) has been condensed with ethyl quinoline-3-carboxylate (I) in presence of alcohol-free sodium ethylate to 3':*N*-methylpyrrolid-2-onyl-3-quinolyl ketone (III). This is then converted into 3-quinolyl- γ -methylamino-*n*-propyl ketone (IV) by hydrolysis with

* In the above formulæ R stands for

fuming hydrochloric acid. The amino-ketone is subsequently reduced catalytically to 3-quinolylamino-*n*-propyl carbinol (V) in poor yield. On treatment with red phosphorus and hydriodic acid, the iodo derivative, α -3-quinolyl- δ -methylamino-*n*-butyl iodide (VI), is obtained which passes into the racemic benzonicotine (VIII) in potassium hydroxide solution.

Benzonicotine containing an asymmetric carbon atom (C*) like nicotine, should have two optical isomers. In the racemic form the new base has been physiologically tested and has been found to be one-third as active as natural *l*-nicotine. The detailed experiments of its pharmacology are being published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3' : *N*-Methylpyrrolid-2-onyl-3-quinolyl Ketone.—To alcohol-free sodium ethylate (6 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) was added ethyl quinoline-3-carboxylate (10 g.) dissolved in *N*-methylpyrrolid-2-one (4.9 g.). The mixture was kept at ordinary temperature for 24 hours (exclusion of moisture) during which time it assumed a dark brown colour. After the addition of more benzene (5 c.c.) it was refluxed on the water-bath for 9 hours when a solid brown mass was obtained. To this sufficient ice-cold water was added to dissolve the whole mass. The clear solution was then shaken with ether to remove any unreacted substance and the aqueous layer acidified to congo-red paper with dilute acetic acid, when a yellowish dense turbidity was obtained. The product was extracted with chloroform, the chloroform extract dried over calcium chloride and the solvent distilled off. A brown oil was left behind which solidified on leaving overnight in vacuum desiccator, yield 6 g. It crystallised in plates from dry benzene. m. p. 120°. It is soluble in ether and alcohol and sparingly in ligroin. (Found : C, 70.44; H, 5.60; N, 11.16. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 70.86; H, 5.51; N, 11.02 per cent).

The *monopicrate* was prepared by dissolving the substance in alcohol and adding an alcoholic solution of picric acid (1 mol.), when the picrate separated readily. It crystallised in shining yellow needles from alcohol, m. p. 178°. (Found : N 14.52. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.49 per cent).

3-Quinolyl- γ -methylamino-*n*-propyl Ketone.—The β -diketone (4 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with fuming hydrochloric acid (40 c. c.) at 140-145° for 7 hours. The solution was then diluted with water and made alkaline with sodium carbonate when a turbidity was obtained. After extraction with ether in the continuous extraction apparatus, the ether

extract was dried over sodium sulphate and the ether removed. A brown oil was obtained which distilled at $165-75^{\circ}/0.01$ mm. The ketone is sparingly soluble in water, more so in alcohol and ether and freely in chloroform. (Found : C, 73.55 ; H, 6.93 ; N, 12.30. $C_{14}H_{16}ON_2$ requires C, 73.69 ; H, 7.01 ; N, 12.28 per cent).

The *chloroplatinate* of the ketone was obtained by dissolving the substance in 10% hydrochloric acid and adding a solution of platonic chloride when the salt separated on concentration and cooling. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (75%) in pale brown needles, m. p. $215-20^{\circ}$. (Found : Pt, 30.38. $C_{14}H_{16}ON_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 30.56 per cent).

3-Quinolyl- γ -methylamino-n-propyl Carbinol—The reduction of the 3-quinolyl- γ -methylamino-n-propyl ketone (5 g.) dissolved in hydrochloric acid (10%, 30 c.c.) to the alcohol was effected by hydrogen in presence of palladised charcoal from 25 c.c. of 1% palladium chloride solution and 4 g. of "extra norite." About 700 c.c. of hydrogen were absorbed (theoretical 740 c.c.) in 8 hours, after which there was no further absorption. The filtrate from the mixture was made alkaline to litmus with sodium carbonate solution, when an oily substance separated which was extracted with ether by the continuous process and a reddish oil obtained after removal of ether, yield 3.5 g. The oil is fairly soluble in water and very soluble in alcohol, ether, acetone and benzene, b.p. $200-4^{\circ}/0.5$ mm.

The *chloroplatinate* of the base was formed by dissolving the substance in 10% hydrochloric acid and adding platonic chloride solution in excess. The platinum salt crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. $286-88^{\circ}$. (Found: Pt., 30.31. $C_{14}H_{18}ON_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 30.46 per cent).

The *dipicrate*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $199-201^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 16.17. $C_{14}H_{18}ON_2$, $2C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 16.27 per cent).

α -3-Quinolyl- δ -methylamino-n-butyl Iodide and r-Benzonicotine.—3-Quinolyl- γ -methylamino-n-propyl carbinol (3 g.) and hydriodic acid (d 1.94, 45 c.c.) and red phosphorus (5 g.) were heated under reflux in an oil-bath at $100-110^{\circ}$ for 4 hours. The excess of hydriodic acid was then removed in vacuum at 50° . To the residue were added 35 c.c. of water and the solution filtered off from the red phosphorus, neutralised with potassium carbonate solution and then 40 c.c. of 10% potassium hydroxide added.

α -3-Quinolyl- δ -methylamino-n-butyl iodide was converted on standing for 24 hours into r-benzonicotine, when the clear solution became

densely turbid and was reddish brown in colour. The whole was then extracted with ether continuously, the ether extract dried over sodium sulphate and the ether distilled off. The light brown oily residue (1.8 g.) distilled at $172-175^{\circ}/0.1$ mm. as a colourless oil which assumes a brown colour when left exposed to air. (Found: C, 78.98; H, 7.43; N, 13.17. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2$ requires C, 79.24; H, 7.54; N, 13.20 per cent). Unlike nicotine, benzonitine is not volatile in steam, and is slightly soluble in water.

The *dipicrate* was obtained in ether with an alcoholic solution of picric acid in excess when the salt separated. It crystallised in yellow silky needles from ethyl alcohol, m.p. $224-25^{\circ}$. The picrate is sparingly soluble in both methyl and ethyl alcohol, acetone and chloroform, and insoluble in benzene. (Found: N, 16.78. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 16.71 per cent).

The *chloroplatinate*, prepared in 10% hydrochloric acid solution of the base with excess of platonic chloride solution, is very sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, and insoluble in benzene. It crystallised in light yellow crystals from ethyl alcohol, m.p. $232-34^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 4.59; Pt, 30.98. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires N, 4.50; Pt, 31.35 per cent).

The *chloroaurate* crystallised in shining yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. $239-40^{\circ}$ (decomp.).

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